

Speculation on Quantum Probabilities $W(x)$ (wavefunction) and $W^*(x)W(x)$ Part 2

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In Part 1, we noted that $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents the average number of interaction hits at x for an equilibrium ($p, -p$) scenario. This follows from $\exp(ipx)$ representing the probability for a p hit at x . If $-p$ is also present with the same weight, then $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ is proportional to $\cos(px)$, showing that some x points have low or no probability for a p hit. We argued, however, that these hit points are not at the center-of-mass so the center-of-mass could be at a 0 point. More importantly, average kinetic energy exists at these low or no hit points.

In this note, we wish to examine the average kinetic energy more closely. It is built upon both classical Newtonian (nonrelativistic) ideas and the notion of a probabilistic x point for p hits, given by the probability $\exp(ipx)$. We note that both x and $V(x)$ are continuous, but suggest that a probabilistic picture is compatible with non-continuous impulse hits. In particular, lengths are of the order of 10^{-10} m (atomic) or 10^{-15} m (nuclear) and particle speeds, on the order of 10^7 m/s. This suggests that $V(x)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are associated with ensembles. In the classical case with very slow speeds and large lengths compared to the above numbers, a tiny dx seems to represent an ensemble. Each dx represents an average result $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$. In the quantum case, one needs to use an average based on $\exp(ipx)$ (as argued in Part 1) because $pp/2m$ is seen to exist and change at an interaction point. Thus, $\{\sum_p p^2 \exp(ipx)\} / \{\sum_p p \exp(ipx)\}$ represents an average KE at an x interaction point which may be linked to the $V(x)$ at this same point. One must have kinetic energy at an interaction point for it to be compatible with $V(x)$.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics is based largely on

$$dp/dt = F \quad ((1))$$

which is compatible with special relativity if one uses

$$p = mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((2))$$

((1)) is compatible with:

$$\int F dx = \int dp \, p/m = p^2/2m \quad ((3))$$

((3)) should hold even in a tiny dx region for which $p \rightarrow p^2$, i.e. it should also hold for impulse hits in quantum mechanics, we argue. This begs the question: What does $V(x)$ represent?

In Newtonian mechanics, x space is broken into equal dx units with a constant $p(x)$ in each. An interaction, due to $F = -dV(x)/dx$, occurs in each dx and $p(x)$ changes as mentioned in Part 1.

This then leads to the question: What happens if $V(x)$ is really based on probabilistic impulse hits?

$V(x)$ in Terms of Probabilistic Impulse Hits

Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is the quantum probability for an impulse hit at x (we argue), interaction with a potential $V(x)$ should involve impulse hits. Nevertheless, the $V(x)$ interaction profile is fixed. We note that $V(x)$ is linked with the interaction of a single particle at x , but that it is also associated with a self-energy as shown in the electrostatic potential case. There, $\phi(x)$ is the potential, $q\phi(x)$, with q being the interacting particle's charge, the interaction energy and $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 \text{Electric field}(x) \cdot \text{Electric field}(x)$ being the self-energy. There seems to be a constraint on $V(x)$ even if it may also be thought of in terms of impulse hits. On average, these hits must create an interaction energy at x (for a single particle at x) of $V(x)$.

The issue which arises is that a quantum particle may have a center-of-mass at x , but does not necessarily interact at x due to the probability for a p impulse to be delivered at x of $\exp(ipx)$. This impulse hit leads to p changing to p_1 , i.e. $pp/2m \rightarrow p_1p_1/2m$, and so in Part 1 we associated nonrelativistic kinetic energy in space with the probability $\exp(ipx)$. This does not change the fact that if one had a single particle at x , its potential energy (interaction energy) must be $V(x)$. As a result, in Part 1 we wrote:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is a classical equation. In the quantum case, one must be able to interpret ((4)). $V(x)$ is the interaction energy at x . The kinetic energy is associated with different interaction points linked to $\exp(ipx)$, but one may find an average kinetic energy at x , even though this does not represent the center-of-mass being at x . It is nevertheless an ensemble average of the kinetic energy associated with this point which should then add to $V(x)$ to yield E . One may note that conceptually this is somewhat different from classical physics.

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((5))$$

This suggests that on average one has $KE_{ave}(x)$ at x and that this is also the interaction point (because $\exp(ipx)$ s were used) and so the potential energy at this point should be $V(x)$. One is forced to calculate a kinetic energy ((5)) based on interaction points, not center-of-mass ones. In classical physics the interaction and center-of-mass points are taken to be the same and lie in $dx \rightarrow 0$.

As a result, one has the interesting quantum result that at an impulse hit point one has p and $pp/2m$ and that $pp/2m \rightarrow p_1p_1/2m$ during the impulse. This is strictly classical, the quantum feature is the probability linked with choosing the interaction point. At the same time one must create an ensemble average of all possible $pp/2m \exp(ipx) a(p)$'s in order to find an average kinetic energy associated with a specific interaction point because it is this which is linked with $V(x)$.

Some Numbers

In quantum mechanics, atomic lengths are of the order of 10^{-10} m and nuclear ones of the order 10^{-15} m. Speeds are on the order of 10^7 m/s. As a result, it might be difficult for a single particle to have many impulse hits while traversing 10^{-15} m and an ensemble description of such a situation may be needed. If an impulse hit occurs, it is described by $p^2/2m \rightarrow p_1 p_1/2m$, i.e. by Newtonian mechanics. Given that this is the case, it seems reasonable that one should be able to create an ensemble picture in which each x point is described by an average kinetic energy and potential energy, even if it takes many ensemble instances to create such a thing. Thus, we argue that ((5)) may really be an ensemble average requiring many instances rather than a description of a single system during a tiny interval of time.

In the Newtonian case, $dx \rightarrow 0$ still represents a very large length compared with 10^{-15} m and speeds are very slow compared with 10^7 m/s. In such a case, the ensemble result seems to occur in the single system within dx and so one may immediately apply $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x)$ to dx where $p(x)p(x)/2m$ is really ((5)) within this dx region.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $V(x)$ represents an average and that physically various impulse hits exist. These impulse hits are described by $p^2/2m \rightarrow p_1 p_1/2m$ in the quantum case, but one must have $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ ((6)) on average. In the Newtonian case, $dx \rightarrow 0$ is a very large region and many impulse hits occur, we argue, and so an ensemble average actually exists in dx . In the quantum case, we argue that it does not and that one requires the notion of an ensemble in order to use ((6)). In Newtonian mechanics, $dx \rightarrow 0$ even though being large compared with 10^{-15} m, is mapped to one x point which is taken to be both the interaction point and the center-of-mass point. In quantum mechanics, the interaction point (linked with both $p^2/2m$ and potential energy) is associated with the probability $\exp(ipx)$. To calculate an average $p^2/2m$ one must then use $\exp(ipx)$ and so the average KE at this x point corresponds to the particle interacting at this point, i.e. to $V(x)$ so that ((6)) makes sense.